

Retain Your Rights!

Do you speak Rights Retention and Open Licensing?

RIGHTS RETENTION

ALL RIGHTS RESERVED

It's the default situation of a work indicating the author retains all exploitation rights over his work, and anyone needs to ask him for reusing it except for uses stated as limitations, exceptions or fair use, according to the applicable copyright law. It's the default situation in the absence of the legal notice or terms of use.

AUTHOR'S ADDENDUM

An addendum to a publishing agreement that authors may attach to include their conditions to publish, for instance the retention of certain rights over their work not included in the original agreement.

COPYRIGHT

A rights regime that grants exclusive rights to creators of original works, including literary, artistic, musical, and other creative expressions, allowing them to control how their works are used and distributed.

COPYRIGHT TRANSFER

The document where the original copyright holder grants any or all the rights over a work to a person or entity that then become the new holder.

DISTRIBUTION RIGHTS

The right to make the work accessible to the public through physical copies.

EXPLOITATION RIGHTS

The exclusive rights granted to authors to decide how to use a work including, but not limited to, reproduction, distribution and communication and to make derivative works.

FIRST PUBLICATION RIGHTS

A publisher's exclusive right to publish a work for the first time.

INSTITUTIONAL RIGHTS RETENTION POLICY

An expressed position setting out the practice of retaining sufficient rights for academic works of an institution's employees to make the work immediately openly accessible and reusable.

PUBLIC COMMUNICATION RIGHT

The right to make the work publicly available without the need to distribute physical copies.

REPRODUCTION RIGHTS

The right to make copies of the work.

RIGHTS RETENTION

The action to retain sufficient rights for academic works to enable them to be openly accessible and reusable preferably immediately.

SECONDARY PUBLISHING RIGHTS

The right to republish a work elsewhere once it has been published for the first time immediately or after a period of time. This right, included in some national European legislations, is granted to authors when publishing results from publicly-funded research, regardless of the contract or transfer agreement they might have signed with a publisher.

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OPEN LICENSING

ATTRIBUTION

When reproducing, distributing or communicating publicly someone else's work, there is a requirement to give the correct credit to the original author and, in some licences for example the CC ones, it is further extended to anyone designated to receive attribution.

CREATIVE COMMON (CC) LICENCES

A set of open licensing that grants rights under certain conditions and requirements, depending on the elements of each licence.

DERIVATIVE WORKS

New works based on or adapted from existing works.

EXCLUSIVE LICENCE

A licence that grants exclusive rights to a person or entity, preventing the author from granting similar rights to others and may restrict the author to use the work freely.

NON-EXCLUSIVE LICENCE

A licence that grants rights to a person or entity to use a work but does not prevent the same rights being given simultaneously to multiple parties.

OPEN LICENCE

Legal text that can be used by copyright holders to grant rights to the public for using their works beyond what is allowed by the applicable copyright law by default.

PUBLIC DOMAIN

Where works are not protected by copyright and are freely available for anyone to use, modify, or distribute without obtaining permission.

SHARE-ALIKE

An element in certain Creative Commons licences that requires derivative works to be licensed under the same or a compatible licence.